

GROWTH PERFORMANCE OF NILE TILAPIA (*Oreochromis niloticus*) UNDER DIFFERENT MANAGEMENT OPTIONS USING PLASTIC TANKS

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ABSTRACT

The farmer's choice of management strategy has a big impact on how well tilapia fish are farmed. The purpose of this study was to evaluate the growth performance of Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) under various management options. Three treatments, trial number T1 (extensive system, algae only), trial number T2 (semi-intensive system, algae + supplemental feed), and trial number T3 (intensive system, commercial feed only) were set up in the experiment. Each treatment included three replicates. Over the course of the 24-week trial, the growth metrics and feed utilization were assessed. In terms of bi-weekly weight gain, T2 showed the greatest growth performance (14.50g), followed by T3 (5.26g) and T1 (2.25g). The results showed a significant difference ($P < 0.05$). There was no significant difference in the absolute growth rate ($P > 0.05$). T2 had the greatest mean weight gain (2.526g), T3 came in second (0.605g), and T1 had the lowest (0.061g). In terms of relative weight gain, T2 likewise showed the most significant difference (36.1%), followed by T3 and T1 (20.0% and 10.3%, respectively, at $P < 0.05$). There was a significant difference ($P < 0.05$) in the survival rate between the three treatments: T1 (97.96%) > T2 (54.07%) > T3 (49.82%). T2's FCR was lower (1.6) than T3's (2.9). Compared to T2, T3 showed a greater feed intake (FIT) of 288.3g (161.2g). T1 was not given commercial feed hence, no FCR or FIT calculations were made for it. Fish yield varied significantly ($P < 0.05$), with T2 having the highest yield (0.547), followed by T1 (0.268) and T3 (0.211). This study concludes that a semi-intensive system of production is superior to both intensive and extensive systems, and it is therefore advised for the farming of *Oreochromis niloticus*.

Keywords: Nile Tilapia, Aquaculture, Growth Performance Commercial Fish Feed, Algae, Treatments, Management Systems.

INTRODUCTION

In Nigeria, indigenous fish output is largely not up to par with demand. Nigeria consumes more than 1.5 million tons of fish annually, making it the greatest consumer of fish in Africa and among the globe due to its vast population. Nigeria's annual domestic catch is projected to be 450,000 metric tons, yet the country still imports over 900,000 metric tons of fish (Ozigbo et al, 2013).

The world's fastest-growing protein food industry is now aquaculture. However, management practices hinder the industry's potential to provide the critically required animal protein (Abd El-rhman et al., 2009). To counter this, appropriate management procedures must be implemented. In aquaculture, management plays a crucial part in any enterprise's success. Amos and Bolorunduro (2000) define management in

aquaculture as the prudent integration of labour, materials and facilities, and capital to guarantee projected profit.

According to Okonji and Osayi (2016), tilapia and clariid catfish are the most often utilized fish species in Nigerian fish farms. The Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*), according to Bentsen *et al.* (1998), is the most popular type of tilapia in aquaculture because of its favoured high performance. It is generally acknowledged that a concerted effort is required to protect and enhance the genetic quality of cultivated stocks. It is undeniable that one of the most significant fish species in tropical and sub-tropical aquaculture is the Nile tilapia, *Oreochromis niloticus* (Linnaeus) (Charo-Karisa *et al.*, 2006 and FAO, 2007). This is due to the fact that it is one of the primary global sources of both revenue and animal protein (Sosa *et al.*, 2005). Tilapia farming has rapidly expanded, bringing these fish into many subtropical and temperate parts of the world due to their adaptability and tolerance to a broad variety of settings and the intensification of cultivation systems. It is the second most important cultured fish in the world right now, behind carp, and is expected to be the most significant fish raised in the twenty-first century (Ridha, 2005). As expected, this is presently happening (FAO, 2014).

Except for the semi-intensive culture fed by additional feed, both extensive and semi-intensive Nile tilapia cultures use phytoplankton as natural food. To ensure that there are enough algae, the pond or tank must be fertilized. It is still possible to provide phytoplankton via inoculation. Significant tilapia output can be achieved without the need for additional feeds if the natural productivity of a pond or tank is enhanced by fertilizing or manuring. Fertilizers and animal manures can be utilized to lower the amount and cost of

supplemental feeding, even though the yields are not as great as those achieved with feed. At densities less than 4,000/acre, an increase in natural food has a substantially bigger impact on tilapia production (Rakocy and McGinty, 1989). Globally, tilapia intensive cultivation (using solely artificial feed) in tanks has been growing (El-Sayed, 2006). The major drivers of the intensification of fish farming in plastic cisterns in various nations include a number of variables, including labour cost reductions and simpler stock management (El-Saidy and Gaber, 2005).

Tilapia can develop and reproduce in a variety of environmental settings and can withstand handling-induced stress (Tsadik and Bart, 2007). Because of its high fecundity, there is competition for food. But there are unfavourable effects to tilapia's high reproductive efficiency. Reduction in growth rates at the commencement of sexual maturity and premature and excessive reproduction are typical problems for many tilapia culture methods, resulting in different sizes of small fish output (Lèveque, 2002).

The fish that is cultured the most in Africa and the second most in Nigeria is the Nile tilapia, *Oreochromis niloticus* (Linnaeus). This is explained, among other things, by its capacity to withstand stress brought on by careless handling, the quality of the water, its omnivorous eating pattern, and its remarkably quick development. Nevertheless, this kind of fish is delicate. Its very high fecundity also results in competition for food and space, which slows growth and makes it more likely to be stunted. Additionally, very little fish is cultured in tanks with the extensive management option. Due to the fragility of this species, commercial tank culture is extremely uncommon in Nigeria, and nothing is known about the fish's capacity to flourish in the different fish culture management options using plastic tanks. Therefore, in order to

guarantee that tilapia farmers in Nigeria utilizing plastic tanks see an improvement in fish output, it is necessary to choose the best management approach. Therefore, the primary goal of this study is to assess how well Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) develops in plastic tanks under various management options.

The purpose of this study is to evaluate the growth performance of *Oreochromis niloticus* in plastic tanks with respect to growth rates, feed consumption, survival rates, and production of Nile tilapia under various management approaches.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The goal of the study was to determine how well Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) grew in plastic tanks under various management conditions. It was carried out at the Department of Aquaculture and Fisheries Management experimental tanks, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Benin. There were nine 160-liter plastic (polyethylene) tanks in service.

Experimental Fish

A total of 135 fingerlings of Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) of the same average size, health status, age, and nutritional history, were collected from the concrete nursery tank in the experimental farm of the Department of Aquaculture and Fisheries Management, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Benin, Benin City. Prior to stocking, the fingerlings had a day of acclimation.

Experimental Tanks

Nine plastic containers with similar capacities were employed. These tanks were positioned in columns with outlets and covered with netting to keep the baby fish from escaping while the water was being flushed. The tanks were labeled according to the three treatments (T1, T2, and T3), each of which was replicated three times. T1 was the semi-intensive (algae and

supplementary feed), T2, extensive (just algae), and T3, intensive (only artificial/supplemental feed). T1 and T2 were placed outdoors while T3 was placed indoors (under shade) to discourage the growth of algae.

Fish Stocking

O. niloticus fingerlings were stocked as mixed-sex at the following rates: 15 fish/tank in the extensive system (T1), 15 fish/tank in the semi-intensive system (T2), and 15 fish/tank in the intensive system (T3). The average weight of the fish was 1.75g. Every treatment was replicated three times and allocated to tanks at random.

Fish Diet and Feeding

The feed types utilized for the three treatments are as follows: commercial feed only for the intensive system (T3), and commercial feed plus algae for the semi-intensive system (T2), while algae only was used for the extensive system (T1) which was supplied simply by inoculation from phytoplankton-rich concrete tank water in the departmental farm. For the first 12 weeks of their culture, T2 and T3 were fed a commercial floating pelleted diet (Table 1), and from the 13th to the 24th week, they were fed a different kind of commercial feed (Table 2). The experimental fish were fed to satiation three times a day, in the morning, afternoon, and evening. The quantity of feed consumed was recorded. Feed was manually applied to the fish on the surface of the water within the tanks.

Sampling of Fish

Fish were sampled and weighed once every two weeks, generally in the morning. The 0.01g sensitive electronic scale (Changzhou Xingyun Electronic Equipment Co. Ltd, China, Model No.: WT40002G, sensitivity of 0.01g) was used to weigh a sample or all fifteen of the stocked fish in each tank. Following a partial flush of the tanks' contents, fish samples

were gathered using a sieve and promptly placed in a holding dish that had already been filled with water of a specified weight. This was done to avoid dehydrating the fish and creating stressful conditions that may cause mortality. Every replicate's additional weight was noted.

The fish were immediately put back into their own tanks for culture after being weighed. The tank's water level was kept at the 100-liter threshold to ensure that there was enough water for the culture.

Table 1: Composition of First Commercial Feed for Tilapia

Composition	Starter		Grower
	0.3, 0.5, 0.7 and 1.0	1.7	T1-2,3 and 4.5mm
Crude protein (%)	48.0	40.0	35
Crude fat (%)	8.0	8.0	8
Starch (%)	15.0	22.0	22
Crude fibre (%)	2.0	2.0	3.5
Ash (%)	9.0	7.0	5.4
Phosphorus (%)	1.3	1.3	0.9
Copper (%)	7.5	5.0	5
DE (KJ/kg)	13.7	13.7	13.7

DE = Digestible Energy

Table 2: Composition of second commercial feed

Crude protein	45%
Crude fat	13%
Crude fiber	1.9%
Ash	9.5%
Phosphorus	1.1%
NFE	33.6%
Vit A	15000iu/kg
Vit D3	2000iu/kg
Vit E	200mg/kg
Vit C (stable)	150mg/kg
Copper (cupric sulphate pentahydrate)	5mg/kg

Vit = Vitamins

NFE = Nitrogen free extract

Fish Harvesting

After 24 weeks, the cultured fish were harvested. All the fish in the different tanks were scooped out for the final weight gain and the number of fish in each tank was tallied after the tanks were flushed.

The fish's growth response was ascertained by computing the subsequent parameters:

Mean Weight Gain (g) (MWG)

$$MWG = W_{t_2} - W_{t_1}$$

Where W_{t_1} = initial mean weight of fish at time T1

W_{t_2} = final mean weight of fish at time T2

Growth Response**Absolute Growth Rate (g) (AGR)**

$$\text{Absolute growth rate} = \frac{\text{final mean weight gain} - \text{initial mean weight of fish}}{\text{Time in day}}$$

Relative Weight Gain (%) (RWG)

$$\text{Relative weight gain} = \frac{\text{final mean weight of fish} - \text{initial mean weight of fish} \times 100}{\text{Initial mean weight of fish}}$$

Feed Conversion Ratio (g) (FCR)(Hepher, 1988)

$$\text{Feed conversion Ratio} = \frac{\text{weight of feed consumed}}{\text{Fish weight gain}}$$

Survival Rate (%)

$$\text{Fish Survival (\%)} = \frac{\text{No. of fish that survived} \times 100}{\text{Number of fish stocked}}$$

Fish Yield

$$\text{Fish Yield} = \frac{\text{Total weight of fish harvested}}{168 \text{ days (culture period)}}$$

Water Quality Management

In order to keep the water quality high, T1 (extensive) was flushed infrequently (especially when the algae was depleted) and replaced with new, algae-rich water; T2 (semi-intensive) was flushed often and replenished with new, algae-rich water; and T3 (intensive) was flushed equally and on a regular basis, after which fresh and clean water was impounded into the tanks. Before the water was restored, the tanks were cleaned. During the research period, they were primarily completed in the morning.

Data Analysis

The acquired data were analyzed using the Genstat statistical package, version 8, of the 2005 software package. The Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT) was used to differentiate the means with a 5% probability.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the investigation of the growth performance of Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) under different management options are presented below.

Growth Parameters

The growth parameters include:

Bi-weekly mean weight gain

Table 3 below displays the outcome of the biweekly weight gain in each of the three treatments. The weight gain resulting from the three treatments and the weight gain over time showed significant differences ($P < 0.05$). Consequently, it is noted that the three treatments varied in their biweekly weight increase, with T2 exhibiting the greatest growth performance (14.50g), followed by T3 (5.26g) and T1 (2.25g). Additionally, there are notable variations

in the bi-weekly weight increase over time amongst the three treatments, as seen in Figure 1 below. According to Adams et al. (2013), who pointed out that it may be because of the low natural food (algae) production at the beginning of the experiment, as opposed to the other two systems, which did not feed only on algae, the low biweekly weight growth in T1 was caused by the low concentration of algae. The notion that *O. niloticus* is an omnivore fish species is supported by this result.

Table 3: Bi-Weekly Weight Gain

Time (weeks)	Treatments			Mean time
	1	2	3	
2	1.89	2.30	2.13	2.10
4	2.43	2.97	2.29	2.57
6	1.81	5.48	2.60	3.30
8	2.00	6.26	3.53	3.93
10	2.08	9.52	3.54	5.05
12	1.88	9.44	3.88	5.07
14	2.74	11.90	5.10	6.58
16	2.12	17.02	6.02	8.39
18	2.55	24.18	7.66	11.47
20	2.44	24.50	8.42	11.79
22	2.54	27.96	8.92	13.15
24	2.48	32.48	9.00	14.65
\bar{x} treatments	2.25c	14.50a	5.26b	

NB: Means with different alphabetic remarks are significantly different at 5% probability level.

Absolute growth rate (g/day)

Table 4 displays the absolute growth rate data. According to the results, there were no significant differences in absolute growth across the three treatments ($P>0.05$). On the other hand, the absolute growth rate (AGR) over time differed significantly ($P<0.05$). As a result, the three treatments showed comparable growth trends. Despite the lack of a significant difference in growth between the

treatments, T2 outperformed T1 (extensive) and T3 (intense), with absolute growth rates of 0.037g/day and 0.004g/day and 0.002g/day, respectively. This occurred as a result of T2 always having access to two distinct food sources (algae and supplemental feed), as described by Diana et al. (1994) and Green et al. (2002). In terms of time, expressed in weeks, there was a distinction, though.

Table 4: Absolute Growth Rate (AGR)

Time (weeks)	Treatments			Mean Time
	1	2	3	
2	0.010	0.056	0.027	0.03
4	0.032	0.009	-0.015	0.01
6	-0.025	0.164	-0.052	0.03
8	-0.059	-0.039	-0.072	-0.01
10	0.103	0.175	-0.081	0.07
12	-0.019	-0.238	0.023	-0.08
14	0.075	0.182	0.062	0.11
16	-0.106	0.189	-0.009	0.02
18	0.076	0.146	0.051	0.09
20	-0.039	-0.491	-0.063	-0.20
22	0.008	0.220	0.042	0.09
24	-0.011	0.076	-0.032	0.01
Mean treatments	0.004a	0.037a	0.002a	

NB: Means with different alphabetic remarks are significantly different at 5% probability level.

Mean weight gain (MWG)

Table 5 displays the average weight gain for each of the three treatments. The findings showed that the mean weight increase in the three treatments varied significantly ($P<0.05$). Throughout the 24-week culture period, T2 has the greatest MWG of 2.562g. T3 (0.605) and T1 had the lowest MWG across time, in that

order. Because T2 was well-fed with both natural and artificial diets during the culture period, it performed better. According to Heath and Roff (1996), Coward et al. (1998), and Takagi (2001), T1's low performance may be the consequence of stunted growth brought on by a restricted food supply.

Table 5: Mean Weight Gain (MWG)

Time (weeks)	Treatments			**- Time
	1	2	3	
2	0.137	0.550	0.377	0.352
4	0.547	0.673	0.163	0.461
6	0.200	2.503	-0.477	0.742
8	-0.677	0.810	1.713	0.630
10	0.077	3.257	0.017	1.117
12	-0.193	- 0.080	0.340	0.022
14	0.857	2.467	1.217	1.513
16	-0.627	5.117	0.927	1.806
18	0.437	7.160	1.643	3.080
20	-0.113	0.303	0.720	0.317
22	0.103	3.463	0.517	1.361
24	-0.063	4.520	0.060	1.506
\bar{X} Treatment	0.061c	2.526a	0.605b	

NB: Means with different alphabetic superscript are significantly different at 5% probability level

Relative Weight Gain (%)

Table 6 displays the relative weight increase outcome. Results in Table 8 demonstrated that during the course of the culture period of 24 weeks, there was a significant difference ($P < 0.05$) in the relative weight gain among the three treatments. Compared to the extensive and intensive systems, which have growth patterns that are comparatively comparable, the semi-intensive system (T2) had the most relative weight gain (36.1%) over time. Over time, nevertheless, T3 (20.0%) outperformed T1 (10.3%). However, during culture, the

relative weight gain in the treatments peaked in week 4 (82.7%) and decreased in week 12 (1.3%). This is further explained by the omnivorous eating behavior of *O. niloticus*, which profited from both artificial and natural diets, according to El-Sayed (2006).

Survival Rate

Table 7 below displays the outcomes of the three treatments (extensive, semi-intensive, and intensive systems) throughout the 24-week period that the Nile tilapia culture was subjected to. $P < 0.05$ indicates a statistically significant difference in the survival rates.

Results show that T1 (algae only) had a far higher survival rate (97.96%) than T2 (algae plus supplemental feed) and T3 (commercial feed only), which had survival rates of 54.07% and 49.82%, respectively. Still, there isn't much of a difference between T2 and T3 survival rates. It's possible that surplus and uneaten feed contamination contributed to the low survival rate in T2. The research fish is not

very tolerant to contamination. This is consistent with the findings of Okorie et al. (2013), who found that over feeding causes waste of feed and low water quality, which lowers the survival rate of tilapia. The reason for T1's success is that algae contribute to raising the water's DO level, which keeps the fish habitat safe.

Table 6: Relative Weight Gain (RWG)

Time (weeks)	Treatments			\bar{X} Relative weight gain
	1	2	3	
2	7.8	31.4	21.5	20.3
4	92.5	98.8	56.6	82.7
6	-0.3	97.7	-8.6	29.7
8	-22.8	12.6	68.7	19.5
10	4.0	50.4	2.6	19.0
12	-9.4	3.9	9.4	1.3
14	39.7	23.5	30.9	31.4
16	-10.8	38.8	17.2	15.1
18	20.8	45.0	26.2	30.7
20	-4.3	1.4	7.3	1.5
22	4.4	13.2	7.3	3.3
24	1.8	15.8	1.0	6.2
* \bar{X} Treatments (g)	10.3b	36.1a	20.0b	

NB: Means with different alphabetic remarks are significantly different at 5% probability level.

Table 7: Survival rate

Time (weeks)	Treatments			Mean Time
	1	2	3	
2	100.0	97.77	91.10	96.29
4	100.0	97.77	62.23	86.67
6	100.0	97.77	57.80	85.19
8	100.0	95.53	48.90	81.48
10	97.77	91.10	46.67	78.51
12	97.77	33.30	46.67	59.24
14	97.77	26.67	44.43	56.29
16	97.77	24.47	40.00	54.08
18	97.77	22.23	40.00	53.33
20	95.57	22.23	40.00	52.60
22	95.57	20.00	37.80	51.12
24	95.57	20.00	42.23	52.60
Mean	97.96a	54.07b	49.82c	

NB: Means with different alphabetic remarks are significantly different at 5% probability level.

General Growth Parameters and Feed Utilization

Table 10 displays the feed conversion ratio (FCR), feed intake (FIT), and fish yield of *O. niloticus* after 24 weeks under the different management options.

Feed Conversion Ratio (FCR)

Table 10 below displays the T2 and T3 grand feed conversion ratio values. The findings indicate that there was a substantial ($P < 0.05$) difference in FCR between T2 and T3. Put otherwise, the FCR of T2 (1.6) is lower than that of T3 (2.9), indicating that it converted more feed into flesh. Since T1 was not given an artificial diet, an FCR value could not be determined. According to the table, T2 converted more feed into flesh than T3, which had a higher conversion ratio of 2.9. T2 had a lower feed conversion ratio of 1.6. This is consistent with a research by Ahmed et al. (2014) that found feeding *O. niloticus* a commercial diet resulted in a much greater FCR. Additionally, Ogunji and Wirth (2000) found that *Oreochromis niloticus* given both natural and artificial diets had a higher FCR. Since *O. niloticus* still uses algae, this explains why it turns more feed into flesh when algae are present.

Feed Intake (FIT)

Table 10 below shows the results of the total feed intake for T2 and T3. The outcome demonstrates that feed intake varied significantly between T2 and T3 ($P < 0.05$). It is shown that T3 used more feed and had a higher FIT (288.3g) than T2 (161.2g). This could occur because, in contrast to what was obtained in T2, the commercial feed was the only source of nutrients. Since T1 was not provided commercial feed during the culture period, there was no record of its feed consumption (just algae). According to FAO (2012) and Popma and Masser (1999), tilapias typically don't consume much when they are fed commercial feed after they have eaten algae.

Fish Yield

Table 10 below displays the yield of Nile tilapia cultivated under T1, T2, and T3. At the conclusion of the 24-week culture period, the results indicate a significant difference ($P < 0.05$) in the yield of the three treatments. According to the data, T2 has a higher yield (0.547) than T3 and T1, which had yields of 0.268 and 0.211, respectively. The yields from T3 and T1 don't really differ all that much, although T3 seems to produce a greater yield than T1. This might be because T2 used both commercial and natural diets more effectively than treatments 3 and 1 did, staying consistent with El-Sayed (2006).

Table 8: General Growth Parameter and Feed Utilization

Parameter	Treatments		
	1	2	3
FCR		1.6b	2.9a
FIT		161.2b	288.3a
YIELD	0.211b	0.547a	0.268b

FCR = Feed Conversion Ratio

FIT = Feed Intake.

CONCLUSION

Plastic tanks can be used to culture Nile tilapia under the three management options presented in this study. *O. niloticus* has the best growth

performance thus, as it can be raised most effectively under a semi-intensive management system that uses both algae and supplemental feed.

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